

BULLYING AND PEER RELATIONSHIPS: IT'S INFLUENCE ON STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVE IN A MULTICULTURAL SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

This study employed a qualitative case study design to gain an in-depth understanding of students' experiences and perceptions. The participants consisted of ten high school students aged 14 to 17 from a private school in Molave, Zamboanga del Sur, selected through purposive sampling. Data were gathered using an interview guide questionnaire containing open-ended questions that allowed participants to freely express their experiences and viewpoints. The collected data were analyzed using Colaizzi's phenomenological thematic analysis method to identify significant statements, formulate meanings, and develop thematic clusters.

The findings revealed that cultural differences, family influences, peer acceptance, and social interactions significantly shape students' perspectives on bullying and peer relationships. Students from diverse cultural backgrounds sometimes experience misunderstandings, stereotypes, or exclusion, which may lead to bullying incidents. However, positive peer relationships, cultural awareness, and supportive teacher-student interactions were found to help reduce bullying behaviors and promote inclusivity within the school community. Furthermore, the study highlighted the importance of empathy, respect for diversity, and strong social support systems in fostering a safe and welcoming school environment.

The study concludes that strengthening peer relationships and promoting cultural sensitivity can help reduce bullying and improve students' overall social experiences in multicultural schools. The findings suggest that educators and school administrators should implement inclusive programs, awareness campaigns, and supportive policies that encourage respect, empathy, and positive peer interactions among students.

Keywords: bullying, peer relationships, multicultural school environment, student perspectives, cultural diversity.

Introduction

Bullying is a widespread issue, particularly in educational settings, and it can have a number of negative effects. It

has both physical and psychological impacts, such as being bruised and full of wounds. Students are reluctant to go to

school, feel embarrassed, and feel pressured (Nurhidayah et al., 2021). The alarming prevalence of bullying is underscored by a national survey conducted by the U.S. Department of Education, where 100% of student participants reported experiencing, witnessing, or being aware of acts of bullying during the 2021–2022 school year (National Center for Education Statistics, 2022). This statistic highlights the urgent need for a comprehensive understanding of bullying's multifaceted nature and its impact on diverse student populations.

Bullying is both perpetrated and victimized to a significant extent through peer relationships. Peer rejection predicts traditional and cyberbullying victimization and perpetration, revealing a cyclical connection in which lack of positive peer relations can lead to more bullying, further degrading peer relationships (Li et al., 2024). Prosociality is also inversely linked to bullying, such that positive peer interaction can decrease bullying (Fu et al., 2022).

Furthermore, peer relationships have been found to impact social anxiety, and students who have developed secure and stable relationships with their peers are better able to relate to others, strengthen interpersonal relationships, and are more relaxed in their social activities and less prone to social withdrawal (Shang et al., 2023). Students who are more accepted by their peers have a wider group of friends and are better at building strong relationships (Țepordei et al., 2023). Through the size and quality of their friendship networks, they gain greater protection from feelings of loneliness and isolation.

In the case of bullying, the quality of the interactions between teachers and students is critical. Lower victimization and perpetration of bullying are associated with positive teacher-student interactions. Ethnic minority students are affected by this more strongly, indicating that positive teacher-student relationships can be particularly beneficial in multicultural settings (Bokkel et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2022). Conversely, experiencing teacher violence aggravates bullying issues by creating more aggressive tendencies and negative learning attitudes (Ünlü & Avcı, 2023).

Moreover, social skills and emotional intelligence have a reverse correlation with bullying, implying that strengthening these competencies among students would minimize bullying behaviors. Curricular interventions designed to promote emotional intelligence and perspective-taking abilities have been shown to improve social cohesion and reduce peer violence in ethnically diverse schools (Alan et al., 2021; Trigueros et al., 2020). Furthermore, psychological distress and social media use are self-influencer that are associated with increased bullying involvement, and mental health support should be included in prevention strategies (Sabramani et al., 2021).

In addition, cultural factors such as social norms and ethnicity have a significant impact on bullying patterns in multicultural schools. For instance, norms regarding popularity and bullying can influence bystander behavior, where emphatic concern promotes defender action against bullying (Xie & Ngai, 2020). Such interventions need to consider

these cultural nuances in order to be effective in dealing with bullying in multicultural schools.

Also, bullying at school has a great impact on the physical and mental health of young people in today's society, and its consequences can affect the daily life of individuals for a very long time as well as the problem of social progress (Zhang, 2024). The relationship between bullying and mental health among children aged 11–16 years in Vietnam was studied. They found out that poor mental health can make young people more vulnerable to being bullied at school (Källmén & Hallgren, 2021). Bullying remained at the same level, which was higher among girls in the 9th grade; 4.9% to 16.9%. Having experienced bullying is linked to a higher risk of mental health problems, especially among men where the risk is four times higher. In women, the risk is 2.4 times higher. They also found that poor mental health can make young people more vulnerable to being bullied at school.

Given the complexity of a multicultural school setting, the researchers came up with the idea to investigate the subtle ways in which peer connections and bullying interact to shape students viewpoints. The study will be conducted to explore the connection between peer relationships and bullying experiences, looking at how these elements influence students' perspectives in a multicultural environment. By comprehending these relationships, we may create more effective approaches to lessen bullying's adverse consequences and promote a more welcoming and encouraging school environment.

Objectives

This study aims to determine how bullying and peer relationships influence students' perspective in a multicultural school environment. The study will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What factors affect students' views on bullying and peer relationships within a multicultural school setting?
2. How do students' experiences and understanding of bullying vary according to their cultural backgrounds?
3. How can educators utilize insights from this study to create a more inclusive and supportive school environment for all students?

Methods

This study utilized a case study research design, which is a qualitative approach that involves an in-depth exploration of a particular phenomenon within its real-life context (Yin, 2019). A case study is used when researchers aim to understand complex social issues by examining the experiences and perspectives of individuals or groups in detail. In this research, the case study design was applied to explore how students experience and respond to bullying and how peer relationships influence their perspectives within a multicultural school environment. This approach allows the researchers to gain comprehensive insights into the behaviors, attitudes, and social interactions of students from diverse cultural backgrounds.

This research was conducted at one of the private schools of Molave, Zamboanga del Sur. A private institution known for its

inclusivity—providing opportunities and resources from Grade 7 to 12. The environment has a wide population of students and sections. It is therefore the ideal setting to conduct this study since the researchers were able to get a range of data, various concepts, and distinctive views from the students.

The participants of this study were 10 high school students, selected from different grade levels to provide diverse perspectives on bullying and peer relationships in a multicultural school environment. The group included six females and four males, aged 14 to 17, representing the school's cultural diversity and excluded those who are not enrolled in the school.

An interview guide questionnaire is the primary research instrument used to gather data directly from participants. It contains a list of guided questions that focus on the main topics of the study to obtain detailed and reliable information about participants' experiences, opinions, and perceptions. This instrument includes a set of structured and open-ended questions designed to guide the conversation while allowing participants to freely express their thoughts.

This study used purposive sampling in selecting the participants. Purposive sampling refers to a non-probability sampling technique in which participants are deliberately chosen based on specific characteristics or experiences that are directly relevant to the research objectives, allowing researchers to focus on information-rich cases that can best address the research question (Bullard, 2024).

The researchers followed a procedure in collecting the data for this study. First, formal permission was secured from the school principal through a written request, and coordination with teachers was conducted to identify participants who met the inclusion criteria. A short explanation was then held to inform what is the study's purpose, procedures, and ethical considerations, after which informed consent was obtained from participants who voluntarily agreed to take part. All gathered data were organized, reviewed, and analyzed to identify significant themes. Throughout the research process, ethical principles such as informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation, and proper approval from the school administration were strictly observed to ensure the protection and welfare of the participants.

The data gathered from the participants were analyzed using Colaizzi's (1978) phenomenological thematic method. All responses were carefully read several times to gain a clear understanding of the participants' experiences, thoughts, and opinions regarding bullying and peer relationships in a multicultural school environment. Significant statements related to the research problem were extracted, and formulated meanings were developed to interpret the underlying ideas expressed. These meanings were then organized into clusters of themes. An exhaustive description of the findings was created, and the interpretations were reviewed to ensure accuracy and that they remained unbiased. The process followed Colaizzi's seven-step model: (1) reading all descriptions, (2) extracting significant statements, (3) formulating meanings, (4) organizing

meanings into theme clusters, (5) developing an exhaustive description, (6) producing the fundamental structure, and (7) seeking validation from participants.

Results and Discussion

This part provides an overview of the data gathered from the participants. It presents the results obtained, discussions, and explains how these findings were analyzed and interpreted to answer the study's research questions.

Factors Affecting Views on Bullying and Peer Relationships

The social dynamics within a school environment are significantly influenced by the diversity of the student population. Research indicates that cultural nuances—including traditions, religious practices, and even dietary habits—play a critical role in how students perceive one another and form social bonds. In multicultural settings, a lack of initial awareness can lead to peer avoidance, teasing, or isolation, which hinders the development of healthy peer relationships (Chung et al., 2021; Zannah et al., 2025).

The findings of this study revealed that Cultural Differences and Family Influences emerged as a theme affecting student interactions. These differences often create social barriers that lead to the “othering” of students from minority backgrounds (Borrego-Ruiz, 2025). This is supported by the studies that cultural differences sometimes lead to misunderstandings, which escalate into bullying incidents (Santos, 2021). Students' origins, family, and life experiences also have a big influence on

how they view bullying (Garcia, et al., 2020).

Cultural Differences. Differences in traditions, religion, food, or names often lead to peer avoidance, teasing, or isolation in multicultural schools, hindering relationships until awareness grows. Participants noted that when cultural practices are misunderstood, it frequently results in social exclusion or conflict. These are the insights provided by the participants:

“I have a classmate who came from a different cultural background, and some of our classmate also did not understand his traditions. Because of that they avoided him at first.”
P1

“A student ate different foods from their culture, and some classmates made fun of it.” P7

“There are various situations where culture can affect relationships with friends. For instance, as a Muslim student we are prohibited with many things, some will think that those rules were over and others might respect. That is why from what I have observed we have small amount of peers since some people think that Muslims are scary due to the rules and our cultures.” P9

“Whenever I share my culture about my religion about how I don’t believe in luck my peers would always look at me skeptical and I have to tiptoe around that topic whenever it is brought up to avoid conflict because I know they disagree with that culture of kin.” P10

Family Influence. Family teachings from childhood frame bullying as chaos to avoid, a test of strength, or an evil to combat, directly shaping students’ attitudes and peer interactions. Home environment serves as the primary moral compass for students. It heavily dictates whether a student becomes a bystander or an upstander in bullying situations (Zannah et al., 2025). The participants shared the following insights:

“In some cultures, children are taught to be quiet and show respect, while in other cultures, children are encouraged to be open and talkative. These beliefs affect how student view bullying. If parents teach their children to stand up for themselves.” P2

“When 2 individuals has different cultures and that builds up gap between each other which leads misunderstanding. My family teaches me that you shouldn’t hurt others and must help people who are bullied, because of this, I

think bullying is very bad and should stop.” P5

“Family belief or tradition shape students opinions about bullying through how these things are taught to students since childhood which the students will always carry with them always, like in my case bullying in my family beliefs and tradition is seen as something bad, that is what I was taught since childhood and I carry that belief until now so that’s how family beliefs or tradition can shape a students’ opinions about bullying.” P10

Variations in Experiences and Understanding by Cultural Background

The way students feel and understand bullying is not the same for everyone; instead, it is shaped by their own cultural background. Differences in culture affect how students read social signs. This can lead to big misunderstandings where a normal conversation is mistaken for being mean or angry or what is considered a joke in one culture might be seen as an insult in another, leading to unintended conflicts (Katsantonis, 2021). The findings revealed three themes that emerged regarding variations in experiences and understanding by cultural background. These includes Language Misunderstandings, Varied Reporting Behaviors, and Cultural Response Styles. These themes supported the study that language use leads to misunderstandings

and conflicts to the students. Those who speak a language that others don't are prone to experience bullying (Schihalejev et al, 2019).

Language Misunderstandings.

Language barriers turn innocent tones, jokes, or words into perceived rudeness or anger, sparking conflicts unique to diverse backgrounds. Misunderstandings often happen in schools when students from different backgrounds use different styles of communication. Research shows that the unspoken rules for how to act or joke—vary greatly between cultures. Because of this, a student might use a tone of voice or a specific word that is normal in their culture but feels aggressive or rude to a classmate from a different background (Al Mutairi, 2025). Participants highlighted the following:

“I think language differences can cause misunderstandings.

Sometimes students may say something that sounds rude, but it is just translation problem. I have seen small arguments start because of miscommunication.”P1

“We speak differently, so sometimes we think the other is angry due to their tone.”P5

Varied Reporting Behaviors.

Cultural norms dictate whether students report bullying—silence to preserve harmony, honor, or privacy versus disclosure if independence or respect is emphasized. The decision to tell a teacher or parent about bullying is deeply

influenced by the values a student learned at home. Some students come from cultures that emphasize “independence,” where they are taught to solve their own problems, while others come from backgrounds that prioritize “group harmony,” making them stay quiet to avoid causing trouble (Ntumi et al., 2025). The following are the participants insights:

“I think students report bullying differently. Some students from strict families may be afraid of causing trouble, so they stay silent. Others who are taught to express their feelings may report immediately. From what I observe cultural values play a big role. If culture values respect for authority students might be more willing to tell a teacher but if they are taught to handle problems privately, they may choose not to speak up.” P1

“A student from a culture that values keeping peace may stay quiet and not tell anyone when he or she is bullied. Some students tell a teacher or adult right away. Other students keep it to themselves and don't tell anyone. In some cultures, people are taught to be brave and tell someone when they are bullied.” P4

“For me students from communities with limited trust in institutions may

hesitate to report bullying to school authorities, meanwhile those who are used to formal systems may feel more comfortable filing a report. Cultures that prioritize respect may avoid questioning or challenging peers publicly while those that promote independence may encourage students to defend themselves openly.”
P7

Cultural Response Styles.

Upbringing influences immediate reactions to bullying, from calm silence or emotional restraint to bold intervention against it. When bullying happens, a student’s immediate reaction—whether they fight back, stay calm, or walk away—is often a reflection of their upbringing. Studies on “cultural coping” explain that in some cultures, showing strong emotions in public is seen as a sign of weakness, so students choose to remain silent and composed to maintain their dignity. Other students may have been raised in environments where standing up against unfairness is seen as a moral duty, leading them to intervene immediately when they see others being mistreated (Yang et al., 2023). Below are the participants responses:

“I remember a student who did not react when teased because in their culture, showing emotions in public is not common. Instead of fighting back the student stayed calm and silent. I realized that culture can

affect how someone responds to hurtful situation.” P1

“One example is a student who was bullied but chose to stay silent because in their culture they are taught not to argue or fight back. Their reaction was influenced by how they were raised.” P8

“One of my friends absolutely hates bullying because in their culture, bullying is seen as a crime and is heavily discouraged so whenever she sees someone getting bullied she would immediately call out and stop the bully.” P10

Insights for Inclusive School Environment

Peer interactions in culturally diverse academic settings are significantly influence by how schools address cultural nuances and the underlying factors affecting student views on bullying. To move beyond social barriers and the “othering” of minority students, educational institutions must implement proactive, multifaceted interventions (Gaffney et al., 2021). Practical steps—ranging from awareness programs and clear policies to safe spaces and teacher modeling of respect—are essential to bridging these cultural gaps. The findings revealed one primary theme that emerged for the insights in making inclusive school environment. This is the Interventions and Solutions. The results supports the article from the researchers of Rutgers University which addressed the issue of bullying in

schools and implements strategies to create safety and supportive learning environment.

Interventions and Solutions. Implementing practical steps like awareness programs educate students about diverse cultures and lifestyles, fostering empathy and understanding. Clear policies provide a framework for addressing incidents, ensuring fairness and consistency. Safe spaces allow students to express themselves freely, and teacher modeling of respect sets a powerful example for students to follow. By combining these efforts, the school can create an inclusive environment where everyone feels valued and respected, reducing instances of bullying and promoting a positive school culture (Nocentini et al., 2022).

“Conduct cultural awareness programs, anti-bullying campaigns, and group-oriented programs that help in fostering respect and understanding. Teachers can listen to the students and take bullying seriously and create a safe and respectful classroom. Schools can improve by having clear anti-bullying rules that demonstrate proper behavior and cultural respect as well as student assistance programs.” P2

“Have programs like cultural awareness activities and anti-bullying seminars. These can help

students understand and respect each others differences. Teachers can support students better by listening carefully, being fair, and making sure students feel safe to talk about their problems. Schools can improve by making strong anti-bullying rules and promoting respect for all cultures. They can also organize activities that make everyone feel included.” P8

“Symposiums about respecting culture and how important it is to respect cultures can teach students to build respect towards different cultures and lessen the bullying and misunderstandings happening between their peers with different cultures. Teachers can better support students who experience bullying by calling out the bully and make them understand what their doing is wrong and needs to stop and to put a clear boundary about what is wrong and right and encourage respect towards different cultures inside the school and to support the bullied students and encourage them to speak up about putting clear boundaries towards jokes that can be considered as bullying. Schools can

implement anti-bullying rules in the school, train staff and students to be more accepting about diversity and be more inclusive, and create a safe space for students and staff where they can share their opinions and feel supported. Schools can also work to diversify their curriculum to reflect the experiences and perspectives of all students.” P10

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that bullying and peer relationships in a multicultural school environment are deeply influenced by cultural differences and family beliefs. Cultural differences, while enriching the school community, may also create misunderstandings and social barriers when not properly addressed. Family beliefs and early socialization significantly shape students’ perceptions of bullying and guide their responses to such situations.

Furthermore, variations in cultural norms influence how students interpret behaviors, respond to conflict, and decide whether to report bullying incidents. These differences highlight the necessity of culturally responsive policies and practices within schools. Therefore, fostering an inclusive, culturally sensitive, and supportive educational environment is essential in shaping positive student perspectives and promoting respectful peer relationships.

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. School administrators are encourage to strengthen and institutionalize comprehensive anti-bullying policies that explicitly promote cultural respect and inclusivity. Regular implementation of cultural awareness programs and student support initiatives is recommended. Administrators are encourage also to ensure the establishment of accessible reporting systems and safe spaces that protect students’ well-being.

2. Teachers are encourage to cultivate culturally responsive classrooms that promote mutual respect and open communication. Immediate and consistent intervention in bullying incidents is essential. Educators are encourage to integrate discussions on diversity and inclusion into classroom activities and to model respectful behavior toward all cultural backgrounds.

3. Students are encourage to practice empathy, respect, and cultural sensitivity in their interactions with peers. They are encourage to actively support classmates who experience bullying and responsibly report incidents to appropriate authorities. Developing awareness and appreciation of cultural diversity is vital in strengthening peer relationships.

References

Alan, S., Baysan, C., Gumren, M., & Kubilay, E. (2021). Building Social Cohesion in Ethnically Mixed Schools: An Intervention on Perspective Taking*. The Quarterly Journal of Economics.

- Al Mutairi, Furat. (2025). Language Barriers and their Impact on Effective Communication in Different Fields.
- Bandura, A. (2019). *Social Learning Theory*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall Social Foundation of Thought and Action.
- Banks, J. A. (2020). *Diversity and citizenship education: Global perspectives*. Jossey-Bass.
- Bernardino, J. C., Bautista, J. L., Benedicto, M., Beriña, M. A. E., Besa, R. M., Buenaventura, J., ... & Calacday, C. R. (2025). Linking Family Dynamics, Social Media Use, and Maladaptive Coping in Emerging Adults: A University-Based Correlational Study. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 3(2), 43-50.
- Bokkel, I., Roorda, D., Maes, M., Verschueren, K., & Colpin, H. (2022). The Role of Affective Teacher–Student Relationships in Bullying and Peer Victimization: A Multilevel Meta-Analysis. *School Psychology Review*, 52, 110 - 129.
- Borrego-Ruiz, A. (2025). Ethnic-Cultural Bullying Among Adolescents: Key Insights from Global Evidence. *Cultural Conflict and Integration*, 2(1).
- Brechwald, W. A., & Prinstein, M. J. (2021). Beyond homophily: A decade of advances in understanding peer influence processes. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 31(4), 889–905.
- Brown, B. B., & Larson, J. (2020). Peer relationships in adolescence. In *Handbook of Adolescent Psychology* (3rd ed.). Wiley
- Chung, A., Vieira, D., Donley, T., Tan, N., Jean-Louis, G., Gouley, K. K., & Seixas, A. (2021). Adolescent peer influence on eating behaviors via social media: Scoping review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 23(6), e19697.
- Fel Chen (2019). The effect of cyberbullying victimization, traditional bullying victimization and suicidal ideation among college students: do specific affective problems play a mediate role? *BMC Psychology*, 12, 762.
- Fu, X., Li, S., Shen, C., Zhu, K., Zhang, M., Liu, Y., & Zhang, M. (2022). Effect of prosocial behavior on school bullying victimization among children and adolescents: Peer and student-teacher relationships as mediators. *Journal of adolescence*.
- Gaffney, H., Ttofi, M. M., & Farrington, D. P. (2021). What works in anti-bullying programs? A meta-analysis of effectiveness. *International Journal of Bullying Prevention*, 3(3), 144-156.
- Gao, L., Liu, J., Hua, S., Yang, J., & Wang, X. (2022). Teacher–student relationship and adolescents’ bullying perpetration: A moderated mediation model of deviant peer affiliation and peer pressure. *Journal of Social and Personal*

- Relationships, 39, 2003 - 2021.
- García et. al (2020). Bullying victimization, physical inactivity and sedentary behavior among children and adolescents: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 17, 114.
- Källmén, H., & Hallgren, M. (2021). Bullying and Mental Health Risks Among Adolescents.
- Katsantonis, I. (2021). Cultural Variation in Aggressive Behavior: A Cross-Cultural comparison of students' exposure to bullying across 32 countries. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology*, 19(55), 465–490.
- Kence, S. M. (2021). Multicultural school environments and student well-being. *School diversity perspectives and classmate diversity climate: Relations to student belonging and well-being. Journal of Community Psychology*, 54(1), e70082.
- Kilag et al. (2023). The Silent Epidemic: The Bullying Among Children in Philippine Schools.
- Lamarr, M. A., & Ling, B. N. (2021). Long-term psychological effects of bullying. Exploring the perceived negative and positive long-term impact of adolescent bullying victimization: A cross-national investigation. *Aggressive Behavior*, 48(2), 205–218.
- Li, Q., Chu, X., Yang, Y., & Jia, Y. (2024). The bidirectional relationship between peer relationships and bullying: Evidence from cross-lagged analyses among Chinese children. *Child: care, health and development*, 50 4, e13302.
- Matsumoto, D., & Hwang, H. C. (2020). Cultural influences on emotional expression and perception. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 14(6), e12556.
- Nocentini, A., Palladino, B. E., & Menesini, E. (2022). For whom and under what conditions? A meta-analysis on the moderators of anti-bullying program effectiveness. *School Psychology Review*, 51(4), 488–505.
- Nguyen, T., et al. (2024). Development-in-Sociocultural Context Model of Student Engagement. The development-in-sociocultural context model of student engagement. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 51, 2183–2207.
- Ntumi, S., Upoalkpajor, J. N., & Nimo, D. G. (2025). Culturally responsive assessment of help-seeking behavior among university students: a mediation-moderation analysis of cultural norms, mental health stigma, and digital engagement across cross-cultural contexts. *BMC Psychology*, 13(1), 922.
- Nurhidayah, I., Aryanti, K. N., Suhendar, I., & Lukman, M. (2021). The relationship between peer

- pressure with bullying behavior in early adolescents. *Majalah Keperawatan Unpad/Journal of Nursing Care*, 4(3).
- Olweus, D. (2021). *Bullying at school: What we know and what we can do*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Parekh, B. (2019). *Rethinking multiculturalism: Cultural diversity and political theory*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Researchers from De La Salle University and the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM 2). (2023). High Incidence of Bullying in Philippine Public Schools Alarming.
- Sabramani, V., Idris, I., Ismail, H., Nadarajaw, T., Zakaria, E., & Kamaluddin, M. (2021). Bullying and Its Associated Individual, Peer, Family and School Factors: Evidence from Malaysian National Secondary School Students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18.
- Santos (2021). School climate, moral disengagement and empathy as predictors of bullying in adolescents. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 656775.
- Schihalejev, O., et al. (2019). Cultural and Linguistic Factors Affecting Bullying. Religion and children's perceptions of bullying in multicultural schools in Estonia, Finland, and Sweden. *Journal of Beliefs & Values*, 41(3), 371–384.
- Shang, Y., Chen, S., & Liu, L. (2023). The role of peer relationships and flow experience in the relationship between physical exercise and social anxiety in middle school students. *BMC Psychology*, 11(1).
- Stephen, D. L., Dook, L., & Kence, S. M. (2021). Cultural diversity and bullying among senior high school students. The association between in-class cultural diversity with empathy and bullying in adolescence: A multilevel mediation analysis. *International Journal of Psychology*, 55(5), 769–778.
- Țepordei, A., Zancu, A. S., Diaconu-Gherasim, L. R., Crumpei-Tanasă, I., Măirean, C., Sălăvăstru, D., & Labăr, A. V. (2023). Children's peer relationships, well-being, and academic achievement: the mediating role of academic competence. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14.
- Thomsen, E., Henderson, M., Moore, A., Price, N., and McGarrah, M.W. (2024). *Student Reports of Bullying: Results From the 2022 School Crime Supplement to the National Crime Victimization Survey (NCES 2024-109rev)*. U.S. Department of Education Washington, DC: National Center for Education Statistics.
- Ünlü, M., & Avcı, R. (2023). Examination of Aggression and School Attitudes of High School Students Exposed to Teacher Violence and Peer Bullying. *Journal of School Violence*, 22, 474 - 489.

- Xie, H., & Ngai, S. (2020). Participant roles of peer bystanders in school bullying situations: Evidence from Wuhan, China. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 110, 104762.
- Xie, L., Wen, P., Zhou, J., Li, X., Huang, J., & Li, L. (2024). Association of child maltreatment and school bullying among Chinese adolescents: The mediating role of peer relationships. *BMC Public Health*, 24, 2550.
- Veenstra, R. (2022). On the micro foundations of the link between classroom norms and behavioral development. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 46(2), 163–171.
- Veenstra, R., & Lodder, G. (2022). Introduction to the special section on social norms and social network dynamics. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 46(2), 151–155.
- Yang, J. Y., McDonald, K. L., & Seo, S. (2023). Coping strategies in response to peer victimization: Comparing adolescents in the United States and Korea. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 34(1), 159–172.
- Yin, R. K. (2019). *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods*.
- Zannah, H. A., Rahmat, M., & Anwar, S. (2025). The influence of religious maturity level on bullying behavior among senior high school students. *SCAFFOLDING Journal Pendidikan Islam Dan Multiculturalism*, 7(2), 451–468.
- Zhang, Y. (2024). A review on the impact of bullying in schools. *Lecture Notes in Education Psychology and Public Media*, 42(1), 90–94.